
Deliverable D-JRP22-WP5.2

Workpackage 5

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MEME PERIODIC TECHNICAL REPORT TO OHEJP/COMMISSION (12 MONTHS ACTIVITIES)

Summary of the work carried out

MEME is aiming at filling relevant research gaps highlighted by international agencies for the detection and control of cystic and alveolar echinococcosis. MEME is focusing on standardization, harmonization and validation of existing parasitological and molecular methods, and the development and comparative assessment of innovative molecular tools and biomarkers to detect *Echinococcus multilocularis* (Em) and *Echinococcus granulosus s.l.* (Eg) along the food chain. Production of epidemiological data on the presence of Em/Eg eggs in the food chain is focusing on vegetables for human consumption as well as canine faeces in selected endemic countries. MEME includes integrative activities to harmonize procedures and to improve detection of Eg and Em.

Core activities conducted during the first year of the project:

- Standard Operating Procedures for the sampling of matrices were produced.
- Sampling of different matrices from naturally or experimentally infected definitive and intermediate hosts was started.
- Validation of the established parasitological (Segmental Sedimentation and Counting Technique, SSCT) and novel molecular diagnostic procedures (m-PCRs and MC-RT-PCR assay) was started to detect *E. multilocularis* and *E. granulosus s.l.* in different matrices along the food chain.
- Development and validation of new tools (new molecular markers for *Echinococcus* species from rapid diagnostics to source attribution; new multiplex qPCR for detection and discrimination of Em/Eg and Eg genotypes; sequencing using Region-Specific Extraction (RSE) and NGS for the detection of Em/Eg in complex samples; biomarker discovery in exosomes from sheep plasma for diagnosis of CE infection) was started.
- Start Production of data relevant for epidemiological assessments (contamination of vegetables for human consumption by eggs of Em/Eg; prevalence of Em/Eg in dog faeces; identification of potential risk factors for human CE/AE infection through questionnaires; molecular epidemiology studies on Eg genotype diversity) was started.
- Dissemination of project results at different levels (general public, populations at risk, biologists, veterinarians, clinicians, health authorities, policy makers and media) was also started.

Scientific papers published on peer-review journals under the framework of MEME:

- Cystic Echinococcosis: Clinical, Immunological, and Biomolecular Evaluation of Patients from Sardinia (Italy). *Pathogens*. 9(11), 907. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens9110907>
- A validated method to identify *Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato* at species level. *Infection, Genetics and Evolution*. 85, 104575. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.meegid.2020.104575>
- Bayesian Analysis of Three Methods for Diagnosis of Cystic Echinococcosis in Sheep. *Pathogens*. 9(10), 796. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens9100796>
- Species Detection within the *Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato* Complex by Novel Probe-Based Real-Time PCRs. *Pathogens*, 9(10), 791. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens9100791>
- Microsatellite Investigations of Multiple *Echinococcus granulosus Sensu Stricto* Cysts in Single Hosts Reveal Different Patterns of Infection Events between Livestock and Humans. *Pathogens*, 9(6), pp. 444. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens9060444>
- Casulli, A, (2020), Recognising the substantial burden of neglected pandemics cystic and alveolar echinococcosis, *The Lancet Global Health*. 8 (4):PE470-E471. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X\(20\)30066-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X(20)30066-8)

Work carried out in the JRP/JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

1. WP1: SAMPLING STRATEGY (M25-M48)

The aim of this WP is to collect in the field and in the research facilities and to produce in the laboratory, the biological material needed to implement the activities of MEME. In the reporting period the collection of the samples in the field was started. Participants begin to organize sampling in the field from intermediate and definitive hosts. Part of planned material were collected and preserved for further purposes (red fox intestines and faeces, worms, cysts, dog faeces). Detailed SOPs for sampling of matrices were prepared. In experimental model, *E. multilocularis* strain was maintained in different groups of mice infected at different period in order to have protoscoleces available around every two months. These protoscoleces of *E. multilocularis* were used to infect three red foxes to obtain reference positive faecal material for the validation of methods and the Proficiency Testing schemes of MEME. Moreover, two red foxes were infected by protoscoleces of *E. granulosus* s.s. in order to obtain eggs for the infection of sheep for the proteomic study.

JRP-WP1-T1. SOPs for sampling in matrices (M25-M28)

The following Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) were prepared:

- Sampling of faecal material in dog faeces collected from the environment (WP1T2, Responsible ANSES) and their processing for molecular analysis.
- Sampling of *E. granulosus* cysts from naturally infected sheep and pigs at abattoirs (WP1-T2, Responsible PIWET) and experimentally infected sheep (WP1T3) and their processing for molecular analyses.
- Sampling of faeces and small/large intestines from experimentally infected foxes (WP1-T3, Responsible ANSES) and their processing for parasitological and molecular analyses.
- Sampling of vegetables for human consumption (WP3-T6, Responsible ANSES) and their processing for molecular analysis.

JRP-WP1-T2. Matrices collection in the field from intermediate and definitive hosts (M27-M36)

The aim of this task is to collect different matrices from naturally infected definitive and intermediate hosts for their use in other WPs. Most of participants started to organize sampling from red foxes, dogs, and intermediate hosts. Five hundred and nine intestines of red foxes, 167 intestines of arctic foxes, 100 intestines of raccoon dogs from endemic areas were collected; some of them were examined with SCT/SSCT. From positive intestines *E. multilocularis* worms were isolated. Additionally, faeces from distal part of large intestine were collected. Sixty three red fox intestines from areas supposed to be free of *E. multilocularis* were collected. Moreover, 300 intestines of red foxes from *E. multilocularis* free areas (Ireland) were collected. Other parasites (*Mesocestoides* spp., 5 samples; *Taenia* spp., 4 samples) were isolated from small intestines of red foxes - for specificity controls. Ninety samples of pigs' livers and 100 sheep's livers with suggestive lesions of tapeworm larvae were collected and were prepared for identification. Additionally, few *E. multilocularis* and *Taenia hydatigena* sp. lesions isolated from *Arvicola terrestris* and *E. granulosus* cysts isolated from sheep were collected. Organization of collection of faecal samples from dogs for epidemiological study was started. Participants sent information and collection kits for owners and veterinary cabinet in rural areas of highly endemic regions. Three hundred and eighty faecal samples from dogs were collected in this way. Additionally, hundreds dog faecal samples from environment were collected, all negative for *E. multilocularis* (examined with qPCR) as a potential matrix for validation.

JRP-WP1-T3. Matrices collection from experimental animal models (M27-M48)

ST1. All the authorizations for animal testing have been obtained at ANSES for the infection of mice and foxes with *Echinococcus*. They are in compliance with the ethical authorizations for animal

experimentation (Decree n° 2013-118 of February 1st 2013) and the ethical authorizations for the experimental infection of carnivores by *E. multilocularis* (from mice to foxes) (16-073 N° APAFiS: 20160913348095). Unfortunately, production of matrices (faeces, worm and eggs) from foxes has been delayed for months due to national lock-down consequent to COVID-19 pandemic (absence of workers at the animal facilities). Only mice metacestodes production has been maintained during this period. Metacestodes material (200 µl of protoscoleces) and 200 references DNA/protein samples have been produced. Starting from July 2020, several infected groups of mice were also produced. At the beginning of July, two foxes have been infected with 35,000 protoscoleces from infected mice. Faeces have been daily collected to monitor the infection for 90 days. Collected faeces have been inactivated at -80°C for safety reasons. These faecal samples have been analysed by qPCR and flotation methods. We have obtained reference positive faeces (with or without eggs) for future development of MEME diagnostic protocols. A study about the detection of *E. multilocularis* DNA by copro-qPCR during prepatent and patent infection is in progress in order to obtain a better understanding of *E. multilocularis* DNA detection in fox faeces. At the beginning of October, one more fox have been infected with 50,000 protoscoleces from infected mice. Feces have been daily collected, inactivated at -80°C, and analysed by PCR to monitor the animal infection. At Day 28 we have euthanized the fox and the intestine have been collected and stored at -80°C as reference material for the SSCT Proficiency Testing of MEME.

At the end of October 2020, two red foxes were also infected by *E. granulosus* s.s. protoscoleces from cysts of sheep collected at slaughterhouses in Sardinia (IZSS, Italy). These *E. granulosus* s.s. eggs should be used to infect sheep in Portugal for the proteomic study. The flotations and PCRs at 47 dpi were negative. Analyses of fecal samples by flotation between 60 and 70 dpi will be realized soon to confirm the absence of infection.

ST2. Sheep were selected and kept in animal facilities in Portugal according to animal welfare procedures. Concerning ethics approval for the experimental infection of sheep, this was prepared and submitted to the local ethics committee in Portugal. The ethical authorization for the infection of sheep with *Echinococcus granulosus* eggs have been obtain from the Portuguese Veterinary Authority (DGAV – Direção Geral de Alimentação e Veterinária) in December 2020, in compliance with the Decree 113/2013 of August 7th 2013. A selection of 20 one year old female sheep has been kept in adapted facilities with increased biosafety in Santarém (Portugal, a INIAV research centre).

2. WP2: VALIDATION of PARASITOLOGICAL and MOLECULAR ASSAYS (M29-M44)

The harmonization and validation of selected parasitological and molecular procedures have been impacted by national lock-downs due to COVID-19 pandemic. Some task are delayed, time has been used to collect samples. Validation will include estimates of the analytical and diagnostic performance characteristics of tests.

Publications:

Skrzypek K, Karamon J, Samorek-Pieróg M, Dąbrowska J, Kochanowski M, Sroka J, Biliska-Zajac E, Cencek T. Comparison of Two DNA Extraction Methods and Two PCRs for Detection of *Echinococcus multilocularis* in the Stool Samples of Naturally Infected Red Foxes. *Animals* (Basel). 2020 Dec 11;10(12):2381. doi: 10.3390/ani10122381.

Santuoccu C, Bonelli P, Peruzzu A, Fancellu A, Marras V, Carta A, Mastrandrea S, Bagella G, Piseddu T, Profili S, Porcu A, Masala G. Cystic Echinococcosis: Clinical, Immunological, and Biomolecular Evaluation of Patients from Sardinia (Italy). *Pathogens*. 2020 Oct 30;9(11):907. doi: 10.3390/pathogens9110907.

Santolamazza F, Santoro A, Possenti A, Cacciò SM, Casulli A. A validated method to identify *Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato* at species level. *Infect Genet Evol.* 2020 Nov;85:104575. doi: 10.1016/j.meegid.2020.104575.

Bonelli P, Loi F, Cancedda MG, Peruzzi A, Antuofermo E, Pintore E, Piseddu T, Garippa G, Masala G. Bayesian Analysis of Three Methods for Diagnosis of Cystic Echinococcosis in Sheep. *Pathogens.* 2020 Sep 27;9(10):796. doi: 10.3390/pathogens9100796.

JRP-WP2-T1. Segmental Sedimentation and Counting Technique, SSCT (M29-M36)

The SSCT method was chosen due to its high sensitivity (98.3%) compared to reference SCT and above all a significant reduction of time due to the analysis of only two out of five segments of the whole intestines (Umhang *et al.*, 2011). According to the SOP (WP1-T1), each segment of fox intestines collected in the different countries will be independently analysed for the observation and counting of the number of worms. The data obtained will be used for an international validation of the method using the best combination of two segments resulting in the higher sensitivity. Previous results reported from 117 infected fox intestines from France in the context of the original description of the method will be added. According to the protocol, the analyses of the first four segments of intestines has already started in France, Latvia and Poland and will be extended to other participants during the year. Due to national lock-downs consequent to COVID-19 pandemic, the real start of the analyses will be delayed until the end of 2021.

JRP-WP2-T2. Comparison of multiplex PCRs (M29-M44)

This task focuses on the validation of molecular assays widely used for the detection of *Echinococcus* in definitive and intermediate hosts, targeting mitochondrial and nuclear markers:

Assay 1: Boubaker *et al.* (*PLoS Negl Trop Dis*, 2013), a single-tube multiplex PCR allowing discrimination of *Echinococcus* at the level of species/genotypes.

Assay 2: Trachsel *et al.* (*Parasitology*, 2007), a single-tube multiplex PCR targeting the definitive host for the identification of eggs belonging to *E. granulosus*, *E. multilocularis* and *Taenia* genus.

The assay 1 was tested resulting in conclusion that it is not possible to validate this method because of the unreliability of the molecular markers used in the multiplex PCR. Next step will be the validation of the assay 2.

JRP-WP2-T3. Magnetic Capture - Real Time PCR assay (M29-M44)

The validation of the Magnetic Capture-PCR will be conducted according to stage 3 and 4 of the OIE chapter on validation of diagnostic methods, since basic diagnostic characteristics of the test have already been published. Stage 3 validation means testing the assay in different laboratory settings, using equally aliquoted panels of more than 20 samples sent out to each laboratory. To make this possible, the method needs to be set up and verified before this panel is sent out and tested. So far, we have identified the laboratories interested in participating, we have more or less finished SOPs for the methods and a SOP for the validation is in progress. Reference samples from ANSES was received. Next steps are prepare reference material for setting up and verifying the method in the participating labs, and also arrange workshops for the persons in need. Due to COVID-19, measures limiting personnel access to the laboratories and travel restrictions due to quarantine requirements these workshops have been postponed. We are exploring alternative methods to carry out the training and are in dialogue with the project partners to find a viable alternative for early 2021, such as digital training platforms. Once the method is set up and verified in the labs, the stage 3 validation panel can be sent out. This is planned to take place late summer 2021. Not until the data is analyzed, can stage 3 validation be considered finished.

3. WP3: DEVELOPMENT/VALIDATION of NEW TOOLS and PRODUCTION of DATA RELEVANT for EPIDEMIOLOGICAL ASSESSMENTS (M27-M52)

WP3 aims at generating new innovative tools for rapid detection, differential diagnosis, and tracking of infection, both at large and small-scale settings.

Most tasks of work package 3 are delayed due to the COVID-19 lockdowns as many laboratories were closed. It was therefore not possible to work on several tasks of the work package. In course of the task WP3-T1, samples from various countries worldwide were collected and of these, the mitochondrial genomes of 85 isolates from Turkey (n=47) and Armenia (n=38) were sequenced. Further samples will be collected and analysed by mitogenome sequencing. Four TaqMan® probe-based qPCRs were developed in task WP3-T2. At this stage, they can be used as a single-step genotyping technique for the diagnosis of *E. granulosus* genotypes in four epidemiologically relevant subgroups, i.e. *E. granulosus s.s.* (G1 and G3), *E. equinus* (G4), *E. ortleppi* (G5) and the *E. canadensis* complex (G6, G7, G8 and G10). In task WP3-T4, the study protocol was submitted for approval to the ethics committee in March 2020. Due to the difficulties caused by COVID-19 pandemic, the experimental animal infections for the proteomic study are delayed.

JRP-WP3-T1. New molecular markers for *Em* and *Eq s.l.*: from rapid diagnostics to source attribution (M27-M48)

Following the use of the two published microsatellites EgSca6 and EgSca11 for *E. granulosus s.s.*, the presence of two copies in the genome of EgSca11 complicates its interpretation and prevent its use for phylogenetic analyses. There is a need to substitute this microsatellite by one or several other classical microsatellites. A new screening of the *E. granulosus* genome has resulted in the identification of 15 new microsatellites targets, which are currently evaluated for their polymorphism, reproducibility, limit of detection, quality of the electrophoretic profiles and their specificity. The selected profiles will be associated to EgSca6 in order to obtain a panel with a high discriminatory power allowing highly discriminant identification which is necessary for accurate source attribution and for large phylogenetic studies. *E. granulosus s.s.* DNA samples from North Africa (Morocco, Tunisia) and Europe (France, Moldova) are already available and will be completed by others for testing polymorphism of the microsatellites.

Publication:

M'rad S, Oudni-M'rad M, Bastid V, Bournez L, Mosbahi S, Nouri A, Babba H, Grenouillet F, Boué F, Umhang G. Microsatellite Investigations of Multiple *Echinococcus Granulosus Sensu Stricto* Cysts in Single Hosts Reveal Different Patterns of Infection Events between Livestock and Humans. *Pathogens*. 2020 Jun 5;9(6):444. doi: 10.3390/pathogens9060444.

JRP-WP3-T2. New multiplex TaqMan qPCR for detection and genotyping of *Eq s.l.* and *Em* (M27-M48)

At this stage, Four TaqMan® probe-based qPCRs can be used as a single-step genotyping technique for the diagnosis of *E. granulosus* genotypes in four epidemiologically relevant species and subgroups, i.e. *E. granulosus sensu stricto* (G1 to G3), *E. equinus* (G4), *E. ortleppi* (G5), the *E. canadensis* complex (G6 to G8 and G10) and a single genotype (G8) of the *E. canadensis* complex. The technique also allows differentiating *E. granulosus* samples from other *Echinococcus* or *Taenia* species in samples derived from cystic or faecal material. The qPCRs show high efficiency (ranging between 99% and 106%), analytical specificity (100%) and sensitivity (ranging between 0.6 and 1.4 copies/μl) when used with DNA obtained from cysts or from cloned PCR products. Therefore, they are suitable for a PCR-based diagnosis of cystic echinococcosis in intermediate hosts, including humans as aberrant intermediate hosts. These qPCRs will now be combined to develop a TaqMan probe-based multiplex Real-Time qPCR as a tool for a simultaneous, rapid diagnosis and typing of *E. granulosus sensu lato* and *E. multilocularis* infections. Moreover, experiments are initiated to develop TaqMan® probe-based qPCR assays that differentiate between the individual members of the *E. canadensis* complex (G6, G7, G8 and G10).

Publication:

Maksimov P, Bergmann H, Wassermann M, Romig T, Gottstein B, Casulli A, Conraths FJ. Species Detection within the *Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato* Complex by Novel Probe-Based Real-Time PCRs. *Pathogens*. 2020 Sep 26;9(10):791. doi: 10.3390/pathogens9100791.

JRP-WP3-T3. Detection of Em/Eq in complex samples: sequencing using Regions Specific Extraction (RSE) and NGS (M27-M48)

Initial RSE with NGS have been performed by FLI in Q1-2 2020. Data analysis still has to be performed. Analysis of *E. multilocularis* DNA positive control material (surveillance extraction method) with RSE and Nanopore using Flongle was planned for summer 2020 at NVI. However, restrictions to laboratory access as a result of preparedness measures for the COVID-19 pandemic, has delayed this work.

JRP-WP3-T4. Proteomic study on biomarker discovery in exosomes from animal plasma (M27-M52)

The collection of blood samples for the inception of this activity will start one-year after the infection of sheep with *E. granulosus* egg in Portugal. The approval for the experimental infection was obtained from the local ethics committee in Portugal (INIAV). Because of the COVID-19 pandemic, the production of *E. granulosus* eggs for the infection of sheep was delayed.

JRP-WP3-T6. Contamination of vegetables for human consumption by Em/Eq (M29-M48)

The use of a robust and reliable method to detect few *Echinococcus* spp. eggs from vegetables is a prerequisite to estimate the contamination of vegetables for human consumption. The sensitive technique based on sequential sieving coupled with molecular detection developed by the team of Prof. Peter Deplazes at the Zürich Institute of Parasitology (Guggisberg *et al.*, 2020) was chosen as reference for this multicentre epidemiological study. This method using 300 g of lettuce leaves sample was transferred to ANSES. After sieving and DNA extraction, the detection of *E. multilocularis* DNA was done by qPCR (Knapp *et al.*, 2016) which proved to detect one egg (Ct: 30). Using different spiked numbers of *E. multilocularis* eggs obtained from faeces after experimental infection of foxes (WP1-T3-ST1), the limit of detection in 95% of the time (LoD₉₅) was estimated at three *E. multilocularis* eggs (23/24). When spiked with two eggs a positive detection was obtained for 87.5% (21/24) of the lettuce leaves samples and the one for one *E. multilocularis* egg still needs to be estimated. Additionally, the efficiency of washing lettuce leaves under running water and of spinning with salad spinner and on paper towel are also currently under evaluation. One hundred-sixty lettuces were collected from private kitchen gardens (2 lettuces each) or directly from producers (4 lettuces each) in *E. multilocularis* endemic areas from northern-east France. These analyses detected DNA of *E. multilocularis* in two pools from producers and DNA from *Hydatigera* sp. in six pools from both private kitchen garden and producers. Hundreds of lettuce from others partners are planned to be collected and analysed by ANSES. For each lettuce, the solution obtained at two additional steps (40 µm filter and filtrate from 20 µm) will be also collected in order to later estimate the contamination by other parasites (mainly *Toxocara* spp. and *Toxoplasma gondii*).

JRP-WP3-T7. Prevalence of Em/Eq in dog (faecal samples) from selected geographical areas (M29-M48)

The study design was discussed among participants. The target group are dogs originating from highly endemic areas (high prevalence of *E. multilocularis* in foxes as a proxy), or from regions with relatively high prevalence of *E. granulosus* in sheep. Dogs included in the epidemiological study will be those owned dogs that may have access on feeding on mice potentially infected by *E. multilocularis*. Specific conditions in individual countries will be taken into consideration (i.e. sled dogs from Svalbard in Norway). Samples must be collected individually (i.e. to be identifiable with individual dog described in the questionnaire). Moreover, organization of collection of faecal samples from dogs was started. Number of samples has been statistically estimated. The questionnaire (to complete by owners/vets) with questions concerning data which will be used in epidemiological analysis was elaborated. The following data were included in questionnaire: data about dog (age, breed and sex), place of living,

activity sites and types of activity, deworming (date, frequency and drug), feeding, eating rodents and others. Some participants sent information and/or collection kits to owners and veterinary cabinet in rural areas of highly endemic regions. Additionally, the collection of around 400 hundred of faeces from hunting dogs in France (cooperation with hunting federation) has been launched. Till now, overall, 380 samples from dogs were collected in France, Poland, Latvia and Estonia and preserved for further molecular testing. DNA was extracted from 60 French samples which were preliminary examined with multiplex PCR resulting to the detection of two positive for *Taenia* spp. Next step is to discuss and choose the additional molecular method (qPCR) for the identification of *Echinococcus* spp. in faecal samples.

JRP-WP3-T8. Potential human risk factors by means of questionnaires (M29-M48)

Semi-structured questionnaires on potential risk factors for human infection with CE and AE will be designed and submitted for ethical approval to the relevant committees of the participating hospitals. Upon written informed consent, questionnaires will be administered to volunteers with CE/AE and matched (by age, sex and country of origin) uninfected controls accessing clinical centres participating to the study. This task delayed because of COVID-19 pandemic.

4. WP4: TRAINING, DISSEMINATION and PROFICIENCY TESTING SCHEMES (M27-M54)

This WP focuses on establishing the most effective methods for disseminating project results at different levels and training scientists from institutions participating to MEME in the parasitological and molecular identification of *Echinococcus* spp.

Publication:

Casulli A. Recognising the substantial burden of neglected pandemics cystic and alveolar echinococcosis. *Lancet Glob Health*. 2020 Apr;8(4):e470-e471. doi: 10.1016/S2214-109X(20)30066-8.

JRP-WP4-T1. Trainings (M27-M48)

This task has few months delay because of COVID-19 pandemic. Task WP4-T1 will be achieved in the due time.

Publications and additional outputs

Publication title and DOI reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing fees (in €)
Comparison of Two DNA Extraction Methods and Two PCRs for Detection of <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i> in the Stool Samples of Naturally Infected Red Foxes. https://doi.org/10.3390/ani10122381 https://zenodo.org/record/4384600	YES	Open Access, without embargo period.	Gold Open Access. 1.481,00 €
Cystic Echinococcosis: Clinical, Immunological, and Biomolecular Evaluation of Patients from Sardinia (Italy). https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens9110907 https://zenodo.org/record/4159681	YES	Open Access, without embargo period.	Gold Open Access. 1.389,79 €
A validated method to identify <i>Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato</i> at species level https://doi.org/10.1016/j.meegid.2020.104575 https://zenodo.org/record/4066416#.X6UQMWhKjcc	YES	Open Access, without embargo period.	Gold Open Access. 2.300,00 €
Bayesian analysis to evaluate three diagnostic methods for Cystic Echinococcosis in sheep. https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens9100796 https://zenodo.org/record/4061823#.X6PZI2hKjcc	YES	Open Access, without embargo period.	Gold Open Access. 1.389,79 €
Microsatellite Investigations of Multiple <i>Echinococcus Granulosus Sensu Stricto</i> Cysts in Single Hosts Reveal Different Patterns of Infection Events between Livestock and Humans. https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens9060444 https://zenodo.org/record/3894117#.XvyQ6ygzZM0	YES	Open Access, without embargo period.	Gold Open Access. 654,56 €
Species detection within the <i>Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato</i> complex by novel probe based Real-Time PCRs. https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens9100791 https://zenodo.org/record/4061718#.X6PY3WhKjcc	YES	Open Access, without embargo period.	Gold Open Access. 1.250,81 €
Recognising the substantial burden of neglected pandemics cystic and alveolar echinococcosis. https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X(20)30066-8 https://zenodo.org/record/3730559#.Xn3FalhKi70	YES	Open Access, without embargo period.	Gold Open Access. Invited by Editor of Lancet GH, no cost.